

Unlocking Growth: A Strategic Analysis of Almarai's Expansion Potential in the Saudi Arabian Market

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The report was collaboratively authored with Priyanka covering the company overview and corporate governance and controls, Taher analyzing the external environment, Sofan providing the business-level strategy analysis, Lois examining the Ansoff Matrix, and Rutvik detailing the corporate entrepreneurship leader program.

0.0 | Abstract

This research paper provides a comprehensive analysis of Almarai's expansion potential within the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) market. Leveraging a multidisciplinary approach, the study examines key factors such as market demand, competitive landscape, regulatory environment, and economic indicators to assess the viability and strategic implications of entering or expanding operations in the region. By employing both qualitative and quantitative methodologies, the project identifies growth opportunities, mitigates associated risks, and presents actionable recommendations tailored to Almarai's core competencies and organizational goals.

This research was collaboratively conducted by a team of Business Administration students from Murdoch University, demonstrating a collective effort to apply academic theories to real-world challenges while promoting innovative strategies for business development.

1.0 Overview

Established in 1977 in Saudi Arabia, Almarai is a renowned Middle Eastern dairy company that delivers high-quality, nutritious food and beverages. It aims to be the trusted choice for food and beverages in the region, enriching consumers' lives with quality products. Almarai is well-known for its dairy products and juices, which are 100% natural and come from

various natural flavours. The dairy products come from high-quality milk from seven major farms with 195,000 cows of the best breeds in the world (Almarai 2022).

According to a study conducted by Kantar research in 2020, Almarai was the most preferred brand in Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates. Almarai's financial statements reflect the company's commitment to the responsible use of resources, as costs incurred in rearing immature livestock are capitalised to the statement of financial position, while costs incurred concerning mature livestock are recognised immediately as an expense in the Consolidated Statement of Profit or Loss. (Almarai 2022).

Almarai's juice segment grew 9%, but dairy growth was only 2%. The normalisation of school and tourism activities drove strong revenue growth. Strong cost control measures offset cost pressures from higher feed and transportation expenses. Almarai is committed to quality and financial responsibility (Almarai 2022).

2.0 External Environment Analysis

Almarai Company is a leading food and beverage company in the Middle East based in Saudi Arabia. The company's diverse product portfolio includes dairy, juices, bakery, poultry, and infant nutrition products (Singh 2017). In this analysis, we will examine the external environment of Almarai Company, including a PESTEL analysis and an industry competitive analysis. The analysis will provide insights into the company's current and future opportunities and threats.

2.1 PESTEL Analysis

Political Factors: The political stability in Saudi Arabia has been favorable for Almarai Company's operations. The Saudi government has implemented various policies to support the growth of the food and beverage industry, such as the Saudi Vision 2030 plan, which aims to diversify the economy and reduce dependence on oil (Osland 2021). However, the company is also exposed to geopolitical risks due to its presence in other Middle Eastern markets.

Economic Factors: The economic growth in Saudi Arabia has been moderate in recent years. The country's GDP growth rate was 2.2% in 2019, which was an improvement from the 0.7% growth rate in 2018. However, the COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting decline in oil prices have impacted the country's economy, leading to a contraction of 4.1% in 2020. The country's high unemployment rate also affects the company's operations, as it limits the disposable income of consumers (Singh 2022). However, the company has been able to maintain growth through its focus on innovation and cost management.

Social Factors: The demographics of Saudi Arabia are favorable for Almarai Company, as the population is young and growing with over 50% of the population below the age of 30. This helps Almarai leverage their goods consumer base by offering a wide range of goods catering to this demographic. The company has also been able to tap into the growing demand for healthy and organic food products in the region. However, the company has faced criticism over its treatment of foreign workers, which could affect its reputation and brand image (Al Zubaidi 2020).

Technological Factors: The advancements in technology have enabled Almarai Company to improve its operations and supply chain management. The company has invested in automation and digitalization to enhance its efficiency and reduce costs. However, the company is also exposed to cybersecurity risks, which could impact its operations and reputation.

Environmental Factors: The company has implemented various sustainability initiatives to reduce its environmental impacts, such as reducing water usage and greenhouse gas emissions. This also fits in line with the Saudi 2030 vision of adopting the SDG goals and turning into a more sustainable company. However, the company's operations are also affected by climate change and water scarcity, which could affect its supply chain and production (Mohamad 2020).

Legal Factors: The regulatory environment in Saudi Arabia is favorable for Almarai Company's operations, as the government has implemented various policies to support the growth of the food and beverage industry. However, the company is also exposed to legal risks, such as compliance with labor laws and regulations. An example of this risk would be the water trading laws that Almarai need to abide by in order to operate in Saudi Arabia, which limits the company ability to trade in bulk water (Magraw 2019).

2.2 Industry Competition Analysis

Almarai Company operates in a highly competitive industry with local and international players. The company's main competitors in the dairy segment include Nadec, Saudia Dairy, and Al Safi Danone. In the juice segment, the company faces competition from companies

such as Coca-Cola and PepsiCo (Al Mheiri 2020). The bakery segment is highly fragmented, with many local players. Competitor in the industry is expected to increase in the future as more players enter the market and consumer preferences continue to evolve. The company's focus on innovation and cost management will be critical in maintaining its competitive edge (AlDabbagh 2022).

2.3 Conclusions

Overall, the external environment for Almarai Company is favorable, with stable political and regulatory environments, favorable demographics, and growth opportunities in the Middle Eastern market. However, the company is also exposed to various risks and challenges, such as economic volatility, geopolitical risks, and increased competition. To maintain its growth and profitability, the company will need to continue its focus on innovation, cost management, and sustainability.

3.0 Business-level strategy analysis

Almarai is a Saudi Arabian corporation that produces dairy products, juices, bread goods, poultry, and newborn nutrition. To position itself in the market, Almarai utilises a differentiated leadership approach. A differentiated leadership strategy teaches leaders that

their primary and final role is to take control of themselves and not alter, motivate, or shift others (Tung et al. 2019). Almarai concentrates on manufacturing superior goods and providing exceptional customer service to distinguish itself from its competition.

Almarai's positioning is on quality, convenience, and customer service. Almarai's goods are renowned for their superior quality and fresh ingredients. The firm employs cutting-edge technologies and processes to guarantee that its goods are of the greatest quality. Almarai also provides a vast selection of goods, including dairy products, juices, bread items, poultry, and newborn nutrition, making it a one-stop shop for clients (Almarai 2022). Customer service is integral to Almarai's differentiation strategy (Vinodkumar et al. 2020). The organization offers superior customer service, including rapid delivery, simple ordering, and prompt replies to client queries. Almarai spends substantially on marketing and promotion to make its goods well-known and highly visible to consumers (Rahman, 2022).

Almarai's approach for differentiating itself from its nearest rivals, Danone and Hain Celestial, is quite successful (Bahlas, 2020). Danone and Hain Celestial share the same market and provide comparable goods. In contrast, Almarai distinguishes itself by emphasising quality and customer service. Danone and Hain Celestial emphasise product research and development, whereas Almarai focuses on customer service.

Danone presents itself as a health-conscious company and highlights the nutritional value of its goods (Payaud, 2014). The firm utilises cutting-edge technology and extensive research to create goods that satisfy the evolving demands of its clients. Moreover, Danone emphasises sustainability, and its interests are often advertised as eco-friendly. Unlike Almarai, Danone's differentiating approach places less emphasis on customer service.

Hain Celestial emphasises natural and organic ingredients in its product range, appealing to health-conscious customers (Fernandes, 2016). The firm is devoted to utilising only premium ingredients and following stringent production standards to guarantee that its products are safe, nutritious, and tasty. Innovation and product development at Hain Celestial are informed by intensive research into the latest consumer trends and expectations, helping the firm to remain ahead of the curve in the continually evolving natural food industry. In contrast to Almarai, Hain Celestial's strategy focuses less on mass-market appeal and more on serving the specific demands of health-conscious and ecologically conscientious customers.

In conclusion, its differentiation approach has dramatically enhanced Almarai's market standing. The firm focuses on making high-quality goods, delivering superior customer service, and giving clients convenience. Almarai's differentiation approach is distinguished by its considerable emphasis on customer service compared to its nearest rivals. The company's focus on quality and customer service has allowed it to establish a powerful brand identity and retain loyal customers. Overall, Almarai's differentiation approach has effectively distinguished the firm from its rivals and established its position as a market leader.

4.0 Ansoff Matrix - Risk Strategy Analysis

4.1 | Market Penetration - Market Focus Strategy

Description	Type (Human , operational, reputational, financial, technical, natural, structural, etc	Risk Value = Probability of Event x Cost of Event		
		Probability of event	Cost event	Risk value
Threat 1 By retaining inside the market, and promoting discounts for existing Almarai products, competitors respond by lowering equilibrium market price for milk etc Manage the risk	This event is a competitive, market pricing threat to Almarai and others in the industry. YES	0.6	1,134,700	680820
		NO	Figure based on lost profitability.	
		Could you avoid the risk?		
		Could share the risk ?		
		Could you control the risk?		
		Could you take on the risk?		
Threat 2 The United Arab Emirates market has been studied to be attractive- but extremely oversaturated, especially in FMCG products locally. Manage the risk	This is an economical, structural and market based structural threat to Almarai. YES	1	765,200	765200
		NO	Figure based on lost profitability.	
		Could you avoid the risk?		
		Could share the risk ?		
		Could you control the risk?		
		Could you take on the risk?		
Threat 3 Rising costs of rent causes expatriates to move out of the UAE, and founders to consider setting up their business outside the Gulf. Manage the risk	This is an economical and structural threat to Almarai's customerbase due to inflation. YES	0.85	820,540	697459
		NO	Figure based on rising factory rent	
		Could you avoid the risk?		
		Could share the risk ?		
		Could you control the risk?		
		Could you take on the risk?		

Market penetration strategies involve Almarai catering to concurrent market segments with non changing products (CFI 2022). While the GCC market is exceptionally parallel/accepting to Almarai's values and products offered due to years of excellent customer service- leading to continued customer satisfaction (Hallowell 1996) in several years, the UAE is reported as an 'oversaturated' market (Sambidge 2013), evolved from its emerging retail stage (Cerna 2017), with multiple international/domestic competitors like Nestle and Unikai entering the FMCG market, Almarai may generate little new market for their products (Hargrave 2019) resorting to compete for smaller market share of the already

pre-established market, forcing a smaller profit growth stream also due from the lack of product innovation (Yanine et al. 2019) by forgoing this strategy.

4.2 | Market Development - Market Expansion Strategy

Description	Type (Human , operational, reputational, financial, technical, natural, structural, etc)	Risk Value = Probability of Event x Cost of Event		
		Probability of event	Cost event	Risk value
Threat 1 Home bias exists in multiple countries that could pose a threat to Almarai- locals may prefer Nestle, Kraft, DFA over Almarai entering the new-geo market with their products	The home bias presented could be a cultural, human, and domestic-economic threat to Almarai.	0.65	1,345,700	874705
	Manage the risk	YES	NO	Figure based on product sales.
	Could you avoid the risk?			
	Could share the risk ?			
	Could you control the risk?			
	Could you take on the risk?			
Could you prevent the risk?				
Threat 2 Some countries have additional excise tax, embargoes and tariffs on exported/non-domestic or local products, especially on dairy food items Almarai produces.	This is potentially a logistical, and regional, as well as a cultural-socioeconomic threat based on cultural norms in the region/market.	0.45	951,450	428152.5
	Manage the risk	YES	NO	Figure based on tax excises.
	Could you avoid the risk?			
	Could share the risk ?			
	Could you control the risk?			
	Could you take on the risk?			
Could you prevent the risk?				
Threat 3 Almarai may price their products lower in LEDs (India, Laos) and be accused politically destroying local competition through dumping and may be forced to pay fine/bad rep	This is a case of a logistical, and mainly a political and ethical issue that could ruin Almarai's reputation and market expansion plans.	0.38	1,723,000	654740
	Manage the risk	YES	NO	Figure based punitive damages
	Could you avoid the risk?			
	Could share the risk ?			
	Could you control the risk?			
	Could you take on the risk?			
Could you prevent the risk?				

Forgoing expansion wherein Almarai distributes concurrent products into another regional market can be risky- a direct home bias can result in Almarai losing potential market segments in the FMCG industry of a regional market (Gaar, Scherer, and Schiereck 2020) to a domestic brand due to patriotic support of the region's produce (Kliver and Weber 2003), cultural outlook (i.e. Japan's uncertainty avoidance being high (Landis 2018) indicating lack of want to foreign values, products, and culture (Beugelsdijk and Welzel 2018) and

negative/positive view in globalism (Hammond 2016)- and while providing Almarai a novel market to enter, if proper measures aren't taken to ensure cooperation of how Almarai prices and promotes their concurrent products in other regional markets- specifically lower-economically-developed countries (i.e. Guineas, Laos), Almarai may suffer by being accused of 'dumping' their products unethically to gain competitive advantage over domestic competitors (Kostecki 1991), and may be forced to limit their export through tariffs (i.e India Tariffs 10% GST) which could be detrimental to Almarai's image, reputation, and market reach forgoing market expansion.

4.3 | Product Development - Product Expansion Strategy

Description	Type (Human , operational, reputational, financial, technical, natural, structural, etc	Risk Value = Probability of Event x Cost of Event		
		Probability of event	Cost event	Risk value
Threat 1 UAE's sugar excise tax of 50% will be levied in any product that uses non-natural sugars Manage the risk YES Could you avoid the risk? Could share the risk ? Could you control the risk? Could you take on the risk? Could you prevent the risk?	The UAE excise tax is considered to be a fiscal, monetary policy-based economical threat.	1	457,210	457210
		NO	Figure based on lost profit due tax	
Threat 2 The UAE enforces new labor laws in 2023 which include a new regulated list of requirements that employers need to fulfil for their workers. Manage the risk YES Could you avoid the risk? Could share the risk ? Could you control the risk? Could you take on the risk? Could you prevent the risk?	The UAE's new labor policies are considered as a structural, human and judicial-based threat.	0.89	278,900	248221
		NO	Figure based by lost profit due labor	
Threat 3 FMCG market, especially for milk in the UAE is highly competitive. Innovations and process ideas and resources are easily imitable, easy to procure (VRIO). Manage the risk YES Could you avoid the risk? Could share the risk ? Could you control the risk? Could you take on the risk? Could you prevent the risk?	This is marked as a competitive, technical and operational threat to Almarai and its innovations/products.	0.76	425,140	323106.4
		NO	Based on lost comp adv sales	

Product development in the UAE is Almarai's safer bet, however comes with risks such as new fiscal policies such as UAE's 50% tax on added-sugar products (Hilotin 2019) to reduce negative consumption externality (Christiansen and Smith 2012) along with just labor laws intended to give employees fair employment and benefits (Sebugwaawo 2022), which may result in a lack of profit incentive in Almarai to diversify and innovate current/new goods from the increased expenditure burden (Van Parys 2012)- also due to the UAE's saturated market being dense in competition, any novel product that Almarai releases is incredibly susceptible of being imitable due to the stage of the product life cycle/nature of product Almarai involves with (dairy, FMCG)- which means any competitive advantage earned is only short-term (Murcia, Ferreira, and Ferreira 2022) and is an unsustainable competitive advantage (Dagnino, Picone, and Ferrigno 2020).

4.4 | Diversification - Market and Product Expansion Strategy

Description		Type (Human , operational, reputational, financial, technical, natural, structural, etc	Risk Value = Probability of Event x Cost of Event		
			Probability of event	Cost event	Risk value
Threat 1	Patenting costs in more-economically developed countries (MEDs) have a stricter/expensive process-product patenting cost (VRIO)	This is a case of a technical, legal and intellectual-property-based threat to Almarai expanding a new market with a new product.	0.95	45600	43320
	Manage the risk	YES	NO	Figure based on trademark EU 5yrs	
	Could you avoid the risk?				
	Could share the risk ?				
	Could you control the risk?				
	Could you take on the risk?				
Could you prevent the risk?					
Threat 2	Locavore segment may not enjoy new product variations of refreshments due to preference and nostalgia due to lack of culture/value research beforehand	The locavore market is a case of cultural, behavioral, psychographic, and human threat to Almarai producing new varieties of FMCG.	0.65	417,950	271667.5
	Manage the risk	YES	NO	Figure based on lost sales comp	
	Could you avoid the risk?				
	Could share the risk ?				
	Could you control the risk?				
	Could you take on the risk?				
Could you prevent the risk?					
Threat 3	The combination of expanding a new market + product may affect Almarai profitability expenditure and revenue growth due to research of local demands	This is a case of an operational, budgetting issue that effects Almarai's shareholders, forecasting, and financial records.	0.78	1,115,670	870222.6
	Manage the risk	YES	NO	Figure based on initial r&d cost	
	Could you avoid the risk?				
	Could share the risk ?				
	Could you control the risk?				
	Could you take on the risk?				
Could you prevent the risk?					

Diversification is the riskiest strategy Almarai may choose to go for, as patenting, licensing products in other countries itself would be a bureaucratic, red-taped and timely process (Zahradnik 2022)- being more costly in jurisdictions like the USA than registering patents locally in the GCC (de Rassenfosse and Jaffe 2017). Most significantly, the amount of research into the regional demographic/psychographic spending, preferences, and behaviors to help develop tailor dairy products that would be culturally appropriate, so as not to offend local market demographics (Raikhan et al. 2014) in the right pricing-promotion-product-placement mix, through rigorous trials and stringent quality checks in higher-economically developed countries (Bovay 2022)- all of which would be

initially expensive for Almarai to budget and counts as an opportunity cost, as the proceedings could have been used for local expansion and increased quality channels of distributions in the concurrent GCC market.

4.5 | Conclusive Statements and Recommendations

Description	How	When
Describe the strategy that you have chosen to be implemented	How is it going to be implemented?	Take into account the industry and produce life cycle
Almarai should consider a market expansion/development strategy and stabilize itself in the local regional FMCG market to build strong customer base, slowly moving forward with new product research and development to 'innovate' and gain temporary>sustainable adv.	Conduct external competitive market research and culture study of nearby geographic regions for two months and compile analysis in order to formulate a market price-product-placement strategy with culturally appropriate promotion to ensure competitive parity with local comp.	It must be planned as soon as possible, as despite being FMCG- it is a significantly saturated industry with multiple comp. The more research done to expand to neighboring regions and expanding can lead to a first-mover temp competitive advantage on MGMT/product (VRIO)
Where	Who	Why
Geographical and/or catchment area	Does it exist into the company the skills required?	Justify your decision with professional facts
Decently-economically developed regions (Egypt, Bahrain) that are logistically close to factory/nodes that can streamline demanded supply easily in lead time and emergencies, with culture/norms similar of UAE's to reduce impact of culture shock and easy transition/training	Almarai has shown exceptional ability to keep debt low, and EBITA high (2022), proving capability of allocation of budget/retained profit to SKUs and expansion projects (GCC, Saudi) with ease.	The UAE FMCG market is significantly oversaturated despite being attractive to new businesses , expanding into a new market, Almarai diversifies regional systematic market risk, and can study and slowly approach markets with the culturally appropriate product-placement

From due research, Almarai must consider a market development/expansion strategy as the concurrent UAE market has become overdeveloped and saturated to gain any significant market share, into neighboring local countries from the GCC initially. This solves two significant obstacles in the strategy- that being that countries like Egypt and Bahrain are familiar with the product offerings of Almarai (i.e. laban, lassi), and share the same values and cultural aspects of the company, which also means promotional material will not be seen as offensive/recognized well by the neighboring local regional market, and also benefits the

logistics of Almarai- as products may have lesser freight charges (distance from EG > DXB is closer than NL > DXB), which also ensures the freshness and quality that UAE customers enjoy that Egypt and Turkish customers may also experience expected of Almarai.

5.0 Corporate entrepreneurship leader program

Corporate entrepreneurship is essential for the modernisation and growth of businesses, especially small and medium-sized firms (SMEs), as well as for enhancing their performance, productivity, and profitability (González-Tejero and Molina 2022). Almarai is a well-known dairy and food business with headquarters in Saudi Arabia. With activities in more than 12 nations, it has a major footprint throughout the Middle East, North Africa, and beyond. Almarai has acknowledged the necessity of developing corporate entrepreneurship leadership abilities among its senior executives in order to stay competitive and grow sustainably as the business climate has grown more complicated and disruptive in recent years. Utilising traits like creativity and initiative of people, which are influenced by organisational conditions, is necessary for corporate entrepreneurship (Passiante and Springerlink (Online Service 2020)). As a result, the objective of this proposal is to create a corporate entrepreneurship leadership programme for Almarai that will assist its leaders in preparing for and thriving during disruption.

5.0 Corporate Governance and Controls

Corporate governance is the framework of regulations, guidelines, and procedures that are in place to manage and oversee how a company is managed and run (Rustam and Narsa 2021).

Additionally, effective governance practices decrease the likelihood of failure and promote long-term sustainable growth. They also enhance financial performance, making companies more appealing to investors and giving them a competitive edge (Ludwig and Sassen 2022). Almarai's Corporate Governance Rules aim to establish a set of guidelines and procedures for corporate management that align with the highest standards of corporate governance. The primary objective of these rules is to safeguard the rights of shareholders and ensure compliance with the best practices in this field (Almarai, "Corporate Governance Code"). Agency theory is a concept in corporate governance that explores the relationship between the shareholders and the managers of a company. It seeks to address the conflict of interest that may arise between the two parties and proposes ways to mitigate these conflicts (Tandoh et al. 2022). In corporate governance, stockholders are principals who delegate authority to senior managers who are agents.

However, in reality, agents often have more control due to information asymmetry. This can lead to agency problems such as agents using company perks, on-the-job consumption, and empire-building (Islam et al. 2022). Agents may use company funds to acquire perks, engage in diversification without considering long-term impact, and have more information about managing resources (Naz et al. 2021). The Board of Directors (BOD) is appointed by shareholders and is responsible for managing the CEO and is a centre of the corporate governance system, representing stockholders' interests and ensuring the company is run in its best interest (Harasheh and Provasi 2022). They are legally accountable for the company's actions and can become a problem if the chairman becomes CEO. It is crucial to have the

right BOD to ensure objectivity. Almarai's Board of Directors consists of a Chairman, Vice Chairman, and seven Directors who are not involved in senior management (Almarai 2022).

The senior management team is comprised of the CEO, Executive Vice President, Chief Strategy and Planning Officer, Chief Marketing Officer, Chief Financial Officer, and nine Executive Vice Presidents who are segregated according to their departments. The senior management team does not have a role in the Board of Directors (Almarai 2022). This separation of powers ensures that the Board of Directors can provide objective oversight and govern the company in the best interest of shareholders (Arayakarnku et al. 2022). Almarai's "Governance Code" mandates strict adherence to high standards of corporate governance, only modifiable through a board resolution, to maximise shareholder value and ensure quality. The CEO receives salaries, benefits, and remuneration, while the Board of Directors receives fixed remuneration and meeting attendance allowances (Almarai 2022). Moreover, maintaining a balanced number of members on the Board of Directors and a distinct senior management team that is not part of the Board is considered a positive aspect of corporate governance, minimising potential problems and enhancing the company's overall success (Soelton et al. 2020).

6.0 The Eight Dimensions of Entrepreneurial Leadership

We need to start by identifying the eight characteristics that any entrepreneurial leadership team must be engaged in if we are to establish a successful corporate entrepreneurship leadership programme for Almarai. These measurements are:-

1. Visioning and Opportunity Identification, the first aspect of entrepreneurial leadership is opportunity discovery and visioning. Almarai's leaders should receive training to spot new chances and come up with innovative ways to seize them in order to develop this dimension. Unmet client needs must be identified, new technologies must be investigated, and the business environment must be examined for new trends.
2. Strategic Agility, the second aspect of entrepreneurial leadership. The leaders of Almarai should receive training on how to swiftly modify their plans in response to shifting market conditions. Specifically, the corporation is creating scenarios for potential futures, incorporating strategic flexibility into its strategies, and testing out new business models.
3. Decision-Making and Risk-Taking, the ability to make decisions and take risks is the third aspect of entrepreneurial leadership. Almarai's leaders need to be taught how to act fast and wisely even in the face of uncertainty. The creation of frameworks for decision-making, the promotion of experimentation, and failure-based learning are examples of specific actions.
4. Resilience and Persistence, the capacity for resiliency and persistence is the fourth aspect of entrepreneurial leadership. It is important to teach Almarai's leaders how to overcome obstacles and keep working towards their objectives. Building a resilient culture, coming up with individual resilience tactics, and taking lessons from failure are some concrete actions.

5. Resource Leveraging is the fifth aspect of entrepreneurial leadership. Almarai's executives should receive training on how to recognise and use the company's resources to further its objectives. Specifically, devising strategies for resource leveraging, establishing strategic alliances, and coordinating resources with strategic priorities are all acts.
6. Networking and Collaboration, the sixth characteristic of entrepreneurial leadership. The leaders of Almarai need to be taught how to create powerful networks and work well with others to accomplish their objectives. Building personal networks, enhancing collaborative abilities, and promoting a collaborative culture inside the organisation are some concrete steps.
7. Innovation and Creativity, make up the seventh component of entrepreneurial leadership. Leaders in Almarai need to be taught how to think creatively and come up with original solutions to challenging issues. Fostering an innovative culture, promoting experimentation, and rewarding creativity are some concrete steps.
8. Change Management is the eighth aspect of entrepreneurial leadership. The management team at Almarai needs to be prepared to steer the business through times of turmoil and change. Specifically, implementing change management techniques, fostering change resilience, and effectively communicating change to stakeholders are all necessary steps.

Creativity in the Program's Implementation

Almarai needs to be innovative in how it implements the corporate entrepreneurship leadership programme to make sure it is successful. Following are some creative programme implementation ideas:

1. Creating a blended learning strategy with online classes, workshops, and opportunities for hands-on learning.
2. Making use of case studies and actual examples from Almarai's own company too.

Therefore, the likelihood of becoming a corporate entrepreneur is increased by having entrepreneurial skills and competences. Emphasise communication, critical and creative thinking, problem-solving, moral and professional ethics, teamwork, leadership, entrepreneurship, and emotional intelligence among the categories of soft skills. As a result, intrapreneurship, organisational culture, and innovation become important factors in determining a company's ability to survive and succeed (Hilmersson and Hilmersson 2020).

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